

THE STABILITY OF *cyclo*PROPANE RING THROUGH ADDITION REACTION OF DIAZOMETHANE

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Diazomethane reacts additively with benzalacetophenone and benzalacetone to give pyrazoline derivatives. These loose nitrogens, on heating pass into *cyclo*propane derivatives which are unstable and by opening up the ring and migration of hydrogen they isomerise to ethylenic compounds. Thus, there is the possibility of synthesising substances which should theoretically result by condensation of two different ketones but which are not so obtained in practice.

In the Buchner-Curtius reaction diazomethane or its substitution product reacts additively with a molecule containing a double or a triple bond. Thus, Pechmann (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2950) by condensing diazomethane with acetylene obtained pyrazole (I).

Similarly from fumaric ester and diazomethane Buchner (*Annalen*, 1893, 273, 226) obtained pyrazole-4 : 5-dicarboxylic ester (II). The pyrazoline compounds are generally stable and, when solid, could be crystallised without decomposition. When, however, they are heated, nitrogen is evolved and the pyrazoline ring gives rise to *cyclo*propane ring. For instance, by heating the compound (II) Buchner (*ibid.*, 1893, 273, 216) obtained *cyclo*propane-1:2-dicarboxylic ester (III) and Guha (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1890) synthesised *trans*-caronic ester (III, Me₂ in place of H₂) by condensing dimethyldiazomethane with fumaric ester.

Schlotterbeck (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 479) treated diazomethane with benzaldehyde containing a double bond between carbon and oxygen when acetophenone (V) was obtained according to the following reaction :

*Generally when condensations are attempted between two different compounds of the same class, one or the other of them undergoes self-condensation and the desired product to be formed from two different molecules is not formed (unpublished observation).

and KMnO_4 in water. Above all, when heated with strong hydrochloric acid it gives a quantitative yield of acetophenone; even if a few drops are heated in a test tube, the smell of acetophenone is perceptible. These properties are explained by the structure (IX, R=Ph) which has a double bond and which on hydrolysis gives two molecules of acetophenone. On referring to the literature (cf. Kohler, (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 31, 658) the compound (IX, R=Ph) proved to be diphone obtained by the condensation of acetophenone with itself and was confirmed by comparing the oximes of the substance and of diphone. It seems therefore that the pyrazoline compound (VII) first gives rise to *cyclopropane* compound (VIII) as usual, and that in the latter conditions, (a) and (b) mentioned above, being satisfied, the *cyclopropane* ring undergoes the same change as the ethylene oxide ring (IV).

If the above views are correct, diazomethane should afford a method of synthesising substances which should theoretically result by the condensation of two different ketones, but which in practice cannot be obtained in this way*. For instance, though (IX, R=Me) is expected to be formed by condensing acetone with acetophenone, the condensation does not materialise in practice and the compound does not appear to have been prepared so far.

Benzalacetone (VI, R=Me) therefore was treated with diazomethane when the pyrazoline compound (VII, R=Me) was obtained. This was found to be very stable and on distillation under reduced pressure with or without copper powder it sublimed unchanged. It was then heated at 200° for 4 hours when evolution of nitrogen was complete and the resulting liquid distilled at $108^\circ\text{--}109^\circ/3$ mm. Analysis corresponds to $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ required for the isomeric structures (VIII; IX, and X, R=Me).

Like (IX, R=Ph), the liquid decolorises aqueous potassium permanganate, bromine in CCl_4 and forms a semicarbazone (m.p. 180°). From this behaviour and analogy with the compound obtained from benzalacetophenone (VI, R=Ph) it follows that the *cyclopropane* ring has not survived during heating of the pyrazoline derivative (VII, R=Me) and has been transformed into the structure (IX, R=Me). It cannot obviously be the isomeric γ -benzylidene-ethylmethyl ketone (X, R=Me) which has been described by Harries and Mullar (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 968) as a crystalline solid (m.p. 38°). Further, like (IX, R=Ph) it undergoes hydrolysis on boiling with hydrochloric acid and gives acetophenone.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diazomethane was prepared by a modification of the method described by Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1093). The preparation and all reactions were carried out in a fume chamber.

3-Phenyl-4-benzylpyrazoline (VII, R=Ph).—To 10 g. of benzalacetophenone (m.p. 56°) (Kohler and Chadwell, "Organic Synthesis", 1922, vol. 2, p. 1), dissolved in

dry ether (75 ml.) was added gradually a well cooled solution of diazomethane from 10 g. of nitrosomethylurea (Brochet and Gambier, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1895, *iii*, 13, 533; Bell, *Chem. News*, 1875, 32, 99). When the addition was complete, the flask was fitted with a reflux condenser provided with a calcium chloride tube and left in a thermos at 0°. Next day very fine crystals appeared, which did not increase further even after 4 days. The crystals were removed and after drying weighed 8 g. The ethereal liquid after decomposing the excess of diazomethane with acetic acid gave no more of the product. It was crystallised from alcohol as fine yellowish needles, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 5.4; N, 12.0. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 76.8; H, 5.6; N, 11.2 per cent).

It does not react with semicarbazide hydrochloride or nitrophenylhydrazine.

Removal of Nitrogen by the Action of Heat on the Pyrazoline Compound (VII, R=Ph) and Formation of (IX, R=Ph).—The compound (VII, R=Ph, 6.0 g.) was heated in a test tube with a long air condenser in a sulphuric acid bath, the temperature being gradually raised to 210° and maintained at 210°-220° for 3 hours until the evolution of nitrogen had ceased. The brown viscous oil left distilled at 164°-166°/3 mm., yield 4 g. (Found: C, 87.1; H, 6.0. $C_{16}H_{14}O$ requires C, 86.5; H, 6.3 per cent).

It is a pale yellow, pleasant smelling liquid, which is sparingly soluble in alcohol. It does not react with semicarbazide or phenylhydrazine but decolorises bromine in CCl_4 and aqueous $KMnO_4$. On heating alone it gives the smell of acetophenone

Hydrolysis of (IX, R=Ph).—The liquid (1 ml.) was refluxed with 50% hydrobromic acid (15 ml.) on a sand-bath and then steam-distilled. The distillate on extraction with ether and removal of the solvent gave a small quantity of a liquid, which was characterised as acetophenone by the smell and formation of the semicarbazone, m.p. 198°. When, however, hydrobromic acid was replaced by hydrochloric acid, the hydrolysis was better effected and the yield of acetophenone was almost theoretical. Thus 2 g. of (IX, R=Ph) gave 1.5 g. of acetophenone.

The *oxime* of (IX, R=Ph) was prepared by refluxing for 5 hours 0.5 g. of the substance with 0.25 g. of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in absolute alcohol and pouring in a large excess of water when the oxime separated as a white precipitate. It was crystallised from alcohol as white monoclinic crystals, m. p. 132°, which proved to be the oxime of diphone.

3-Phenyl-4-acetylpyrazoline (VII, R=Me).—Benzalacetone (10 g.) in dry ether (75 ml.) was treated with ethereal diazomethane (150 ml.) from 15 g. of nitrosomethylurea at 0°. On the third day the crystals separating were removed and weighed (8 g.). From the ethereal solution after decomposing

the excess of diazomethane and removing the solvent, a second crop was obtained; the total yield was 11 g. It was crystallised from alcohol in fine light yellow needles, m. p. 96°. It is sparingly soluble in water and ether and soluble in benzene and gives no characteristic colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 6.5; N, 14.3. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2$ requires 70.0; H, 6.5; N, 14.9 per cent).

Its *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m. p. 180°. (Found: N, 28.8. $C_{12}H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 28.6 per cent).

Removal of Nitrogen of the Pyrazoline Compound (VII, R=Me) and Formation of (IX, R=Me).—Like the compound (VII, R=Ph), the pyrazoline derivative (4 g.) was heated for 3 hours and the resulting dark red coloured oil distilled at 109°/3 mm. as a thin yellow liquid having a pleasant smell and turning brown on standing, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 7.0. $C_{11}H_{12}O$ requires C, 82.5; H, 7.5 per cent). It decolorises bromine in CCl_4 and aqueous $KMnO_4$ very readily.

Its *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from alcohol as fine needles, m. p. 184°. (Found: N, 19.8. $C_{12}H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 19.4 per cent).

Hydrolysis of (IX, R=Me).—The compound (1 g.) on boiling with strong hydrochloric acid for 2 hours and on steam distillation gave a small quantity of a liquid, which was characterised as acetophenone.

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